

Direct and derivative spectrophotometric method for the determination of nickel(II) with 2,4-dihydroxy benzaldehyde isonicotinoyl hydrazone

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Abstract : A simple and sensitive spectrophotometric method has been developed for the determination of nickel(II) in aqueous medium. The metal ion forms an yellow coloured soluble complex with 2,4-dihydroxy benzaldehyde isonicotinoyl hydrazone (2,4-DHBINH) at pH 6.0 with λ_{\max} at 400 nm. Beer's law is obeyed in the range of 0.059–1.17 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of Ni^{II}. The molar absorptivity and the Sandell's sensitivity of the method are $4.00 \times 10^4 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and 0.0015 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ respectively. The interference of various diverse ions has been studied. The complex has a 1 : 1 [Ni^{II} : 2,4-DHBINH] stoichiometry. A method for the determination of nickel(II) by first order derivative spectrophotometry has also been proposed.

Keywords : Direct and derivative spectrophotometry, determination of nickel(II), substituted hydrazone.

Many organic reagents are proposed for the spectrophotometric determination of nickel¹⁻⁴. Some of these proposed methods are less sensitive², some involve extraction into organic solvents and some require use of surfactants⁴. 2,4-Dihydroxy benzaldehyde isonicotinoyl hydrazone is synthesized in our laboratory and used as a reagent for the spectrophotometric determination of thorium, zirconium, molybdenum and titanium ions⁵. In the present paper, we have reported a sensitive and rapid direct spectrophotometric method for the determination of nickel(II) in microgram levels using 2,4-dihydroxy benzaldehyde isonicotinoyl hydrazone (2,4-DHBINH). The reagent 2,4-DHBINH, reacts with nickel(II) in the pH range 4.0–8.0 forming an intense yellow coloured precipitate, which is soluble in 30% dimethylformamide showing maximum absorbance at 400 nm in the pH range of 5.0–7.0. The yellow colour is stable, showing constant absorbance for more than 48 h. A highly selective first order derivative spectrophotometric method is also developed for the determination of nanogram quantities of nickel(II).

The method has been applied for the determination of nickel(II) in steel alloy sample and vegetable oil (hydrogenated ground nut oil) and compared with those obtained from AAS method.

Results and discussion

The absorbance spectra of 2,4-DHBINH and [Ni^{II}-DHBINH] complex are recorded in the wavelength range

350–550 nm at pH 6.0 against the buffer solution and reagent blank respectively. The complex shows absorption maximum at 400 nm where the reagent shows negligible absorbance. Hence, analytical studies are made at 400 nm.

It is observed that the yellow colour is formed between Ni^{II} and 2,4-DHBINH in the pH range of 4.0–8.0. A study of the effect of pH on the colour intensity of the reaction mixture shows that maximum colour is obtained in the pH range of 5.0–7.0. Hence, analytical studies are carried out at pH 6.0. A 10-fold molar excess of 2,4-DHBINH is essential for complete and constant colour development. Excess of the reagent has no effect on the absorbance of the complex. The yellow colour of Ni^{II}-2,4-DHBINH complex is stable 30% aqueous DMF (v/v) for more than 48 h. DMF should be added before the addition of the reagent to prevent the precipitation of the Ni^{II} complex.

From the calibration plot, it is observed that Beer's law is obeyed in the concentration range of 0.059–1.17 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of Ni^{II}. The molar absorptivity of the complex at 400 nm and pH 6.0 is calculated as $4.00 \pm 0.04 \times 10^4 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Sandell sensitivity is found to be 0.0015 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$. Other statistical data derived for the present method are as follows : the standard deviation for the determination of 0.07 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of Ni^{II} is ± 0.004 . The correlation coefficient (r^2) for the calibration curve is calculated as 0.9992. The composition of the complex is determined by Job's method and mole ratio method and found to be

1 : 1 [Ni^{II} : 2,4-DHBINH]. The stability constant of the complex is determined as 8.97×10^5 by Job's method.

Survey of literature⁶ reveals that the metal ions coordinate to azomethine nitrogen and phenolic oxygen donor atoms of the ligand. Based on the stoichiometry of the complex, the following structure may be assigned to the complex species of Ni^{II}.

Effect of diverse ions :

The effect of various diverse ions in the determination of Ni^{II} is studied to find out their tolerance levels in the present method. The tolerance limit of a foreign ion is taken as the amount that caused an error in the absorbance value by $\pm 2\%$. The data are presented in Table 1. Large amounts of commonly associated cations and anions do not interfere in the determination of nickel(II). Ag^I, Rh^{III}, Au^{III} and Hg^{II} are tolerable up to 8, 5, 15 and 25 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ respectively in zero order method while their tolerance limits are 100, 250, 400 and 500 μg in first derivative method (Table 1). This shows that the first derivative method is more selective than zero order method.

Determination of nickel(II) by first order derivative spectrophotometry :

The first order derivative curves recorded for the experimental solutions showed the maximum derivative amplitude at 430 nm. The derivative method was found to be more sensitive than direct spectrophotometric method. In the first derivative mode Beer's law is obeyed in the range 0.025–1.80 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of Ni^{II}.

Determination of nickel(II) in an alloy steel and vegetable oil samples :

Preparation of steel and alloy sample solutions :

A 0.1–0.5 g of the sample was dissolved in 2 ml HCl + 10 ml HNO₃. The resulting solution was evaporated to a small volume. To this 5 ml of 1 : 1 H₂O : H₂SO₄ mixture was added and evaporated to dryness. The residue was dissolved in 15 ml distilled water and filtered

through Whatman 41 filter paper. The filtrate was collected in a 100 ml volumetric flask and made up to the mark with distilled water. The solution was further diluted as required.

Preparation of vegetable (groundnut) oil sample solution :

100 g of hydrogenated groundnut oil (edible) was dried in an hot air oven at 100 °C and subsequently dissolved in 20 ml mixture of 1 : 2 : 5 H₂SO₄ : H₃PO₄ : HNO₃. The contents were heated until sulfurous fumes were evolved and the volume was reduced to about 5 ml. A little quantity of distilled water was added and filtered through an acid washed Whatman 41 filter paper into a 100 ml volumetric flask and made up to the mark with distilled water.

Procedure :

A suitable aliquot of the sample solution was treated with 1 ml of 0.05 M sodium phosphate in a buffer medium of pH 6.0 and filtered through Whatman filter paper. The filtrate was collected into 10 ml volumetric flask and treated with 0.5 ml of 0.2 M sodium thiosulphate to mask copper(II). 3 ml of dimethylformamide and 0.2 ml of 2,4-DHBINH (1×10^{-2} M) were added and made up to the mark with distilled water. The absorbance was measured at 400 nm against the reagent blank and the amount of Ni^{II} present was calculated from calibration plot. The results are presented in Tables 2 and 3.

Experimental

2,4-Dihydroxy benzaldehyde isonicotinoyl hydrazone (2,4-DHBINH) was prepared by condensing 2,4-dihydroxy benzaldehyde isonicotinoyl hydrazone in methanol⁷ (m.p. 290 °C). The structure of the compound was established by IR, NMR and elemental analysis and shown as

A dimethyl formamide solution of the reagent was used in the studies. Stock solution of Ni^{II} (0.01 M) was prepared by dissolving requisite quantity of (NH₄)₂Ni(SO₄)₂·6H₂O (A.R., B.D.H.) in 100 ml of doubly distilled water and standardized⁸. Buffer solution of pH 4–7 were prepared by mixing 0.2 M sodium acetate and 0.2 M acetic acid and the pH was checked using a pH Meter. pH 8.0 was maintained using 0.2 M sodium ac-

Table 1. Tolerance limits of diverse ions

pH = 6.0, amount of Ni^{II} = 0.587 mg ml⁻¹

Ion	Tolerance limit (µg ml ⁻¹)		Ion	Tolerance limit (µg ml ⁻¹)	
	Zero order	First derivative		Zero order	First derivative
Tartrate	2800	3000	Ca ^I	2500	2800
Sodium thiosulphate	2200	2500	K ^I	2500	2700
Bromate	2000	2200	Fe ^{III}	500 ^a	550 ^a
Thiourea	1500	1650	Na ^I	450	500
Nitrate	1500	1600	Mg ^{II}	100	120
Thiocyanate	1100	1210	Pb ^{II}	100 ^{b,c}	130 ^{b,c}
Ascorbic acid	700	870	Ce ^{IV}	70	80
Iodide	700	800	Ba ^{II}	70	75
Phosphate	450	500	Cd ^{II}	70	70
Fluoride	380	420	Cu ^{II}	60 ^{b,c}	66 ^{b,c}
Oxalate	30	35	Mn ^{II}	50	55
Citrate	Interferes	-	W ^{VI}	40	44
			Al ^{III}	30 ^d	30 ^d
			Mo ^{VI}	20 ^d	22 ^d
			Zr ^{IV}	10	10
			Pt ^{II}	10 ^b	10 ^b
			Pd ^{II}	10 ^b	10 ^b
			Zn ^{II}	10 ^{b,c}	10 ^{b,c}
			Ag ^I	8	100
			Rh ^{III}	5	250
			Au ^{III}	15	440
			Hg ^{II}	25	500

^aMasked with phosphate. ^bMasked with sodium thiosulphate. ^cMasked with thiourea. ^dMasked with fluoride. ^eMasked with citrate.

Table 2. Determination of nickel(II) in alloy steel samples

Amount of nickel Direct spectrophotometry

Sample	Direct spectrophotometry			First derivative		
	Amount present (%)	Amount found* (%)	Error (%)	Amount present (%)	Amount found* (%)	Error (%)
Copper nickel alloy ^a	31.20	31.35	0.5	31.20	31.10	-0.3
Alloy-NTPC- Ball bearing material ^b	10.00	9.60	-2.0	10.00	10.15	1.5

*Average of six determinations.

^a67% Cu; 31.2% Ni; 0.083% Fe; 0.08% Mn; 0.29% Si.

^b65% Fe; 10% Ni; 15% Cr; 4.5% Cu; 2% Mn.

Table 3. Analysis of vegetable oil (ground nut oil)

Sample	Amount of Ni ^{II} found (µg/g)					
	Direct spectrophotometry			First derivative		
	AAS method	Present method*	Error (%)	AAS method	Present method*	Error (%)
Vegetable oil (Hydrogenated ground nut oil)	0.43	0.44	2.32	0.43	0.42	-2.32

*Average of six determinations.

etate. Shimadzu UV-Visible spectrophotometer (Model UV 160A) and Elico pH meter LI 120 were used for absorbance and pH measurements respectively.

Procedure :

Direct spectrophotometry :

In each of a set of different 10 ml volumetric flasks, 5 ml of buffer solution (pH 6.0), 0.2 ml of 2,4-DHBNH ($1 \times 10^{-2} M$) and 3 ml of dimethylformamide were taken. Variable amounts of nickel(II) were added to these flasks and made up to the mark with distilled water. The absorbances of the resultant solutions were measured at 400 nm against the reagent blank and plotted against the amount of nickel(II).

First derivative spectrometry :

For the solutions first derivative spectra were recorded in the wavelength range of 350–550 nm. The derivative peak height was measured by peak-zero method at 430 nm. The peak height was plotted against the amount of nickel(II) to get calibration curve. Linear calibration graphs were obtained and calibration equations were calculated as $A = 0.688C + 0.0008$ for zero order data and $A = 0.366C - 0.0001$ for the first derivative data by fitting experimental data where A is measured absorbance and C is the concentration of the absorbing species.

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